

IMPACT OF COVID-19 LOCKDOWN ON ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

On 30 January 2020 India reported its first confirmed case of the corona virus infection in the state of Kerala. The person affected by corona virus had a travel history from Wuhan, China. India witnessed a surge in confirmed cases of corona virus after people who attended the Tablighi Jamaat religious congregation at Nizamuddin Markaz in Delhi started testing positive for the virus, which was held in mid of March, the meeting is estimated to have been attended by more than 5,000 members including foreigners. The Indian government had already traced 95percent of its members and was on the way of contact tracing. This paper aims at studying the advent of the pandemic in China and India. Moreover, it intends to analyze the impact of COVID 19 lockdown on entrepreneurs in India. A small survey has been made during the first nationwide lockdown of 21 days, in which a total of 110 responses have been collected.

Keywords- Corona virus, COVID 19, Lockdown, Entrepreneurs, Business, Economy, Pandemic, Contagion

INTRODUCTION

Corona virus disease (COVID-19) is a disease caused by a newly discovered corona virus which is communicable in nature. Most of the people getting infected with this COVID-19 virus are supposed to be experiencing respiratory illness from mild to moderate and recover without requiring special treatment. Older people, and people with some history of medical problems like cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory disease, diabetes and cancer are more likely to develop serious illness. The best way of preventing and slowing down the transmission of this virus is to be informed about the COVID-19 virus, the disease its causes and the way it keeps spreading. Protect yourself and other people from infection by washing your hands or using an alcohol based rub frequently and not touching your face. The COVID-19 virus spreads mostly through droplets of saliva or discharge from the nose of an infected person when he/she coughs or sneezes, so it is crucial to practice respiratory etiquette like by coughing or sneezing into a flexed elbow. As of now, there is not any specific availability of vaccines or treatments for COVID-19. However, there are many ongoing research and trials evaluating potential treatments to treat the disease. World Health Organization will be providing updated information as soon as clinical findings become available.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

- 1- To study briefly the origination of COVID 19 in China.
- 2- To study the advent of the deadly COVID 19 and its impact in India.
- 3- To analyse the impact of COVID 19 lockdown on entrepreneurs in India.
- 4- To suggest measures to entrepreneurs to survive in the contagion.

RELEVANCE OF THE PAPER

This paper signifies the detailed analysis of advent of COVID-19 and the impact of nationwide lockdown on entrepreneurs in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research has been carried out through a small survey during the first phase of nationwide lockdown of 21 days throughout the country. Responses were collected with the help of a questionnaire and a total of 110 responses have been collected in the 21 days. The data so collected through the questionnaire were further analyzed using graphs and charts. For the brief analysis of the COVID 19 arrival and the pandemic situation, some data have also been collected through secondary sources such as published articles in various websites.

This paper is only limited to the impact of the pandemic nationwide lockdown on entrepreneurs in India. So, it might not reveal the overall status of the country or world.

COVID 19 IN CHINA

The disease at first had originated from a Wuhan seafood market where the wild animals, including marmots, birds, rabbits, bats and snakes, are traded illegally. Corona viruses are

known to spread from animals to humans, so it was thought that the first people infected with this disease were a group of stallholders from the seafood market – tapered it from contact with animals. The game of finding a villain for the novel corona virus had begun soon after the viral outbreak started making international headlines late last year. The first thing to get targeted was the Chinese eating habits. It was rebutted by health experts. But by that point, it surfaced that China initially attempted to cover the outbreak. Reports appeared saying that the doctor who alerted about the novel corona virus outbreak and went public with his views was harassed by the Chinese authorities. That was the time when prompt action by China could have nipped this viral enemy within the bud. On December 31, China formally informed the World Health Organisation about the novel corona virus outbreak. In next three weeks, China had to enforce a lockdown not only in the epicenter of Wuhan but in all the provinces and districts affected by Covid-19. Meanwhile, China told the WHO that the source of the novel corona virus might be a seafood and meat market in Wuhan. Experts dived into postulating that the virus came from bats and entered into humans through a yet to be recognized intermediary animal. By the end of February, China had shown clear signs of having contained the spread of novel corona virus infection. The global outbreak, however turned into a pandemic scale. The wet market in Wuhan was shut down for inspection and cleaning on January 1, but by then it appears that Covid-19 had already started to spread beyond the market itself. On January 21, the WHO Western Pacific office said the disease was also being transmitted between humans – evidence of which is clear after medical staff became infected with the virus.

COVID-19 IN INDIA

On 30 January 2020 India reported its first confirmed case of the corona virus infection in the state of Kerala. The person affected by corona virus had a travel history from Wuhan, China.

Religious meeting leads to surge in cases- India witnessed a surge in confirmed cases of corona virus after people who attended the Tablighi Jamaat religious congregation at Nizamuddin Markaz in Delhi started testing positive for the virus, which was held in mid of March, the meeting is estimated to have been attended by more than 5,000 members including foreigners. The Indian government had already traced 95percent of its members and was on the way of contact tracing

Indians on quarantined cruise ship Diamond Princess- Again the latest corona virus cases of India were reported from the Diamond Princess cruise ship quarantined off the coast of Yokohama in Japan. A total of 16 people from India were tested to be positive for the virus on the ship as of 26 of February. A total of 132 passengers and six crew members from India are reportedly on board the ship. A total of 124 Indian nationals including five foreign nationals were tested negative for the virus were evacuated in a special flight on 27 February.

Measures taken to control the Wuhan corona virus spread by India- The Indian government has announced a number of preventive measures to be taken to minimise the entry and spread of corona virus. A control room operational 24×7 to address queries was launched.

Nation-wide lock-down- India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi appealed to Indians to avoid gatherings in mass. He requested each and every citizen to observe a nation-wide curfew or janta curfew on 22 March 2020 from 7 am to 9 pm. People were urged to not leave the house on that day unless and otherwise it's for emergency need. The citizen curfew was a forerunner to the nation-wide lock-down announced on 26 March.

A nationwide lock down was announced and was imposed all across the country from 26th of March to 14th of April 2020, which would in turn result in curbing the spread of corona virus pandemic. Observers state that the lockdown has slowed the growth rate of the pandemic by 6 April to a rate of doubling every six days, from a rate of doubling every three days earlier. As the end of the lockdown period approached the state government and other advisory committees recommended on further extension of the lockdown period. Firstly, the governments of Odisha and Punjab extended the state lockdowns to 1 May, followed by Maharashtra, Karnataka, West Bengal and Telangana. On 14 April, Prime Minister Narendra Modi further announced for the extension of the nationwide lockdown until 3 May, with a conditional relaxation after 20 April for the regions where the spread has been controlled.

Evacuation measures- The Government of India arranged for the evacuation Indian citizens. The health condition of all of them was monitored on a daily basis.

Corona virus testing and quarantining returnees at Indian airports- Starting from 04 March India mandated complete screening at all airports in the country given the increase in corona virus imports. Thermal screening has been installed at 21 airports including those in Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Chennai, Bengaluru, Hyderabad, and Cochin to check for corona virus in India.

Impact on India's trade with China- With China under lock-down, India is expected to witness a major impact on imports and exports in various industries including pharmaceuticals, electronics, mobiles, and auto parts. China is the largest exporter to India, which is then followed by the US and UAE. In 2018, China exported goods worth \$90.4bn to India and accounted for 14.63percent of the exports. In the year 2017, electronics components, telecom instruments, computer hardware and peripherals, organic chemicals and industrial machinery for dairy were the top five things imported by India accounting for 46 percent of the imports from China.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON ENTREPRENEURS OF INDIA

Startups are more vulnerable- As a result of preventive measures taken by government of India to curb the spread of the pandemic i.e COVID-19, the small businesses, startup companies and entrepreneurs are more likely to be the vulnerable groups. The preventive measures have caused disruption to these both socially and economically.

Decline in productivity- No one can ever be doubting these tough and unprecedented times, but the collective impact of the loss of staff productivity spread over weeks and possibly months will be very much tough to handle for businesses across India. Whether it's the massive number of employees using their employee benefits like healthcare and burdening startups or the declining productivity of employees, getting through the other end of this pandemic will mean surviving a number unprecedented challenges

The supply-chain breakdown- The problems in the supply chain are turning out to be a biggest challenge for the startups within a wide range of sectors, such as healthcare and technology. As the matter is getting out of the control of entrepreneurs and small businesses, the dysfunctionality of the supply chain is further raising concerns about surviving the pandemic. Besides, for startups that are associated with third-party firms for regulatory, industrial, and legal operations are also facing delays and challenges. The soft supply chain, which also includes of essential tasks like customer services, data acquisitions, and administrative functions are creating another side of vulnerabilities for startups. As most of the startups have relatively undiversified revenue flows, the supply chain is presenting to be a big challenge in terms of both goods and services. This obstacle will create problems like meeting the deadlines and orders in the short-run and impact the goodwill in the long-run.

Closing down the premises- As part of the preventive measure, government have implemented the practicing of social and commercial lockdown, except for healthcare and other necessary business. The closing down or restriction of running operations is extremely affecting the performance of startups and other organizations. For a lot of small businesses, their management systems are either not adequately established as a result of which it can't be fully taken online. This is again turning out to be another reason for concern. Even though authorities have ordered businesses to shut down their premises, and as part of the social distancing, employees are expected to function as a virtual workforce without letting their productivity drop, which is a bit too much difficult , given the current situation. As the coronavirus continues to spread throughout the world, particularly in urban areas, it only increases the chances of more workplaces closing down or going virtual.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Hit by the COVID-19 Lockdown, no matter how established are the businesses, they are experiencing major effects and have to re-work on managing, operating and re-visiting their business plan. Most businesses are facing the challenge to keep rotating their financial wheels amidst the uncertainty. The impact of the nationwide lockdown on small businesses and enterprises may be more brutal due to the scarce resources and cash reserves. Moreover, it will have a key impact on the economy of the country, because all business sectors result in low revenue.

A small survey has been done during the lockdown. The targeted audiences are business persons. A sample of 110 respondents has been collected with the help of a questionnaire.

Age group: Out of the total response of 110 samples, 16.7 percent belong to age group of 20-30 years, 50 percent belong to the age group of 30-40 years, 20 percent belong to 40-50 years age group and 13.3 percent belong to 50-60 age group.

Type of Business concern: During the survey, it has been found that 40 percent of the total respondents are engaged in essential commodity business whereas, the rest 60 percent comprises of food (20.91percent), education (9.09 percent), clothes (10.91 percent), online business (13.64percent), and others (5.45 percent).

Number of employees: It is also found that 45 percent of the respondents had below 10 numbers of employees / staffs engaged in their business concern.

How lockdown affected business operations, sales and revenue: In the present survey, it is found that 83.3 percent of the total responses have commented that the lockdown has seriously affected their business operations, sales and revenue to a great extent. The rest whereas, also agree to be affected by some extent. So, may it be a small business or large one, this contagion has affected all the business entities. Not only operations, the pandemic has also affected the new sales which further resulted in the revenue sources being blurred.

Manage communication: As per the responses collected in the survey, most of the businesses are carried out on an offline basis. So, there has been a record of no communication to a maximum of phone call. Only a few people get to communicate online through whatsapp or other video calling apps.

Manage livelihood: Almost 100percent of the responses so collected agree to manage their livelihood during the pandemic situation to a maximum of 2 months without any new sales.

Loan Payment: Business concern mostly relies on banks and other financial institutions to get their funds to run the business smoothly on a daily basis. Without any new sales, 66 percent of the respondents agree to repay their loan through saved money, availing EMI moratorium provided by RBI etc. Moreover, the other 34percent claim to have no loan.

Help People: It has been found out during the survey that 50percent of the respondents tend to feed stray animals with their surplus funds, in this pandemic situation. The rest 50 percent claims to help poor people by giving them food and financial assistance.

Payment and help to Staffs: As in case of business concern, the entrepreneurs keep rotating the cash on a regular basis. 47 percent of the entrepreneurs' response claim to make their staff payment as required. However, 20 percent of the respondents have somehow managed to make part payment to the staffs and 33 percent of the total respondents are still unable to pay their party/staffs. This is mainly due to the sudden downfall in the business revenue. But, some entrepreneurs also claim to help their regular employees by feeding them and their families as well as providing them necessities.

Financial help: Due to the uncertainty of the pandemic situation getting normal, the entrepreneurs are almost not thinking of approaching any lender, bank or financial institution for financial assistance as they don't see the capacity of repaying the loan as well as interest in due time.

Splitting of Regular Customers: During the survey, it was found that 40 percent of the respondents agree that the splitting of their regular costumers due to the nationwide lockdown. This is so because the shutdown of shops for almost 2 months pushes the customers to find some substitutes to their needs.

Reduction in Annual Income: Out of 110 respondents, 65 percent of the businessmen have accepted the fact that the nationwide lockdown would surely reduce their annual income by 70 percent, due to no new sales. However, 20 percent of the entrepreneurs claimed that their annual income would reduce by 50percent and have tried to find some substitute income source in order to earn their livelihood and the rest 15 percent anticipate of having 30 percent reduction in their annual income due to the pandemic situation.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

The entrepreneurs will have to adapt a new structure and survive the scarcity and slowdown caused due to the lockdown. The following set of aspects could be adapted by the entrepreneurs:

1. *Track expenses*- It has become really important for the people of all categories to assess their expenses and revenues which can assist in planning for the contagion.
2. *Check feasibility*- It is highly imperative to track the current model of the business, financial metrics, the cash flows, impact on new sales, collections, credit cycles and potential bad debts.
3. *Plan policies*- It is of utmost importance to plan policies and be prepared for the next 3-18 months. If the pandemic continues for more than 6 months, the entrepreneurs will surely have to re-assess their business strategy and reduce variable expenses to certain extent.
4. *Secure investments*- In order to extend the continuity, businesses can approach existing investors for additional financial assistance.
5. *Transparent communication*- Communication with employees, staffs, customers, creditors etc via phone calls, whatsapp, video calling apps etc will help the business to understand the perception of buying and selling of products and services.
6. *Maintain relationship*- During the contagion, it is understandable that the payment might get delayed. In such case, businesses should give sufficient notice regarding the delay so that the creditors/ suppliers can also be prepared.
7. *Adapting optional business*- Some small businesses also try to mitigate the loss to some extent in their present business by adapting relatable optional business to face the financial crisis.

The nationwide pandemic situation would seriously hit the economy and affect the customer flow as there would be loss of purchasing power. Moreover, the source of income of businesses will be affected and maintain market strategies would be next to impossible in the contagion. The lockdown would slow down the economy as sales revenue and profit in not only the business concerns but also in all sectors would be decreased. Along with restricted

cash flow, the sources of incomes will be affected as money rotation in the economy will be disturbed to a great extent.

REFERENCES

1. https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_1
2. <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/china-coronavirus>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_coronavirus_pandemic_in_India
4. <https://www.pharmaceutical-technology.com/features/coronavirus-affected-countries-india-measures-impact-pharma-economy/>
5. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/small-biz/hr-leadership/leadership/survival-strategies-for-businesses-during-covid-19-lockdown/articleshow/75371157.cms>
6. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/small-biz/hr-leadership/leadership/survival-strategies-for-businesses-during-covid-19-lockdown/articleshow/75371157.cms>
7. <https://www.business2community.com/startups/how-will-the-outbreak-of-covid-19-affect-the-entrepreneur-and-startup-ecosystem-02299555>
8. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/policy/rbi-steps-to-help-mitigate-impact-of-coronavirus-lockdown-on-biz-industry/articleshow/74846423.cms?from=mdr>
9. <https://www.expresscomputer.in/guest-blogs/survival-during-pandemic/53864/>

QUESTIONNAIRE**Email:**.....**Age Group:**

- 20-30 31-40 41-60

Employment:

- Student Profession Business Unemployed

Type of Business Concern:

- Essentials Food Education
 Clothes Online Business Others

Number of employees/staffs in your business:

- Below 10
 10-50
 50-100
 100 above

Has COVID 19 Lockdown affected your business operation?

- Yes
 No

Has COVID 19 Lockdown affected Sales/Revenue of your business?

- Yes
 No

How do you manage to make business communication? (Work from Home)

- Over Phone
 Over Whatsapp
 Over Skype
 No communication

How long do you expect to manage your livelihood in this lockdown without any new sales?

- Not at all
- For 2 months
- For 3 months
- For 6 months

Do you have any loan payment (EMI) due in any bank?

- Yes
- No

If Yes, How are you going to repay the EMI dues without any new sales?.....

In the case of a surplus, how would you help people?

- Help society
- Help poor people
- Help poor vendors
- Feed stray animals

Have you done with your party payment/ staff payment?

- Yes
- No

In the case of a surplus, how would you help your staffs in their need?

- Provide food
- Provide financial assistance
- No help

Have you talked with banks/ financial lenders about financing needs?

- Yes
- No

According to you, does this lockdown reflect in the splitting of your regular customers?

- Yes
- No

How will the annual income reduce due to the lockdown?

- Reduce by 30%
- Reduce by 50%
- Reduce by 70%

With the serious hit on the economy, will the lockdown affect the customers?

- Yes
- No

If yes, How?

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How would this pandemic situation slow down the economy?

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What steps have you taken to mitigate the loss to your business due to COVID 19 lockdown?

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